

RESULTS OF THE CLINICAL AND MICROBIOLOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF THE ANTISEPTIC DRUG FARGALS AND 1% BENZKETOZONE IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS WITH REMOVABLE ORTHOPEDIC STRUCTURES.

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Abstract.

Pathological changes in the oral cavity contribute to the development of various dental diseases. The increase in the incidence of periodontal diseases and dental caries is the reason for the increased demand of patients with diabetes for dental care. According to R.I. Runge (2014), 53.7% of patients with diabetes need orthopedic dental treatment. Dentures, even for patients without general somatic pathologies, have a number of side effects. Removable dentures have the greatest impact on the organs and tissues of the oral cavity. Violation of the microcirculation of the tissues of the prosthetic bed, the function of salivation and factors of local immunity of the oral cavity contributes to the formation of dental plaque, which entails a change in the microflora of the oral cavity, both quantitatively and qualitatively.

Keywords: dental system, metabolic syndrome, microangiopathy, periodontal status, gingival margin, hypersalivation, oral fluid.

Fargals and 1% Benzketozone in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus were carried out in relation to the patients' removable dentures. For this purpose, we randomly selected 20 patients using removable dentures, comparable in gender, age, type and time of use of the removable orthopedic structure. Of these, 10 patients used the antiseptic drug Fargals and 1% Benzketozone as a method of hygienic care for removable dentures. 10 patients in the comparison group used Corega antiseptic soluble tablets for these purposes tabs. To obtain reliable information and the possibility of objective assessment of significant indicators, all those examined were asked to use the selected method of hygienic care for 1 week once a day. Method of using antiseptic soluble tablets Corega tabs is known: 1 tablet was dissolved in 150 ml of warm running water, the prosthesis was placed in the resulting antiseptic solution for 15 minutes once a day. After the allotted time had passed, the prosthesis was removed from the solution, rinsed generously under warm running water and used for its intended purpose. Preliminarily, for all those examined, the one-time effectiveness of each recommended method of hygienic care for removable dentures was determined by calculating the reduction of denture contamination using the method of S. B. Ulitovsky - A. A. Leontyev (2008). In the observed patients, before applying the recommended methods of hygienic care for removable dentures, the denture cleanliness index 126 developed by S. B. Ulitovsky and A. A. Leontyev (2008) was at the "very bad" level. The values of this indicator changed significantly after just a single use of the selected methods of hygienic care. The use of the antiseptic drug Fargals and 1%

Benzketozone led to the prosthesis cleanliness index according to the method of S. B. Ulitovsky and A. A. Leontyev (2008) 2.8-3.0 and 3.2-3.5 for antiseptic soluble Corega tablets tabs . Therefore, the reduction index of contamination of removable dentures when using the antiseptic drug Fargals and 1% Benzketozone was 45.5-49.0%, which indicates a good degree of cleansing of removable dentures, and 36.4-41.8% for antiseptic soluble tablets Corega tabs – “satisfactory degree of cleansing of the prosthesis.” When examining patients, it was found that after 1 week of using the selected methods of hygienic care for removable dentures, the index of denture cleanliness developed by S. B. Ulitovsky and A. A. Leontyev (2008) in people who used the antiseptic drug Fargals and 1% Benzketozone was 2.0-2.5, which corresponds to a good level of hygiene. In patients using Corega antiseptic tablets tabs, – 3.0-3.5, which corresponds to a satisfactory level of hygiene. It should be noted that in all patients using the antiseptic drug Fargals and 1% Benzketozone for hygienic care of removable dentures, no visible pathological changes were detected on the mucous membrane of the denture bed after 1 week. In patients who used Corega antiseptic soluble tablets for hygienic care of removable dentures tabs , only in 40% of cases there were no visible pathological changes on the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed. In 60% of cases, chronic catarrhal stomatitis of focal localization was detected on the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed. The results of the study are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Results of assessing the condition of the mucous membrane of the denture bed of patients, depending on the method of hygienic care for removable dentures.

To assess the effectiveness of the microbicide effect of using the antiseptic drug Fargals and 1% Benzketozone, a single treatment of 18 removable dentures was carried out.

Table 1. Characteristics of the composition of the microflora colonizing the internal and external surfaces of removable dentures when using the antiseptic drug Fargals and 1% Benzketozone after 1 week, (% , M±m)

Microorganisms	Composition of microflora located on the inner surface of a removable denture with the drug Fargals and 1% Benzketozone (n=18)		Composition of microflora located on the outer surface of the prosthesis treated with Fargals and 1% Benzketozone (n=18)	
	Occurrence percentage	lg CFU/tampon	Occurrence percentage	lg CFU/tampon
Family Enterobacteriaceae	88.90%	4.25±0.32	0.00%	0.00±0.00
Including Klebsiella spp.	11.10%	5.00±0.00	0.00%	0.00±0.00
Enterococcus spp.	94.40%	4.50±0.50	0.00%	0.00±0.00
S. aureus	5.60%	4.00±0.00	0.00%	0.00±0.00
S. saprophyticus	88.90%	4.80±0.49	0.00%	0.00±0.00
P. aeruginosa	33.30%	4.83±0.31	0.00%	0.00±0.00
Candida albicans	44.40%	4.38±0.18	0.00%	0.00±0.00
Candida krusei	5.60%	4.00±0.00	0.00%	0.00±0.00
Note: bold font - statistically significant differences at p≤0.05				

Based on the results of the study, we can conclude that this method has an absolute microbicidal effect. At the end of 1 week of use, the method of hygienic care for removable dentures chosen for each group, biological material was collected to determine the composition of the microflora colonizing the inner surface of the removable orthopedic structure. As a result of the studies, it was established that when using the antiseptic drug Fargals and 1% Benzketozone, the inner surface of removable dentures was colonized by such microorganisms as: α hemolytic Streptococcus and Staphilococcus spp. to a degree not exceeding lg 4.88±0.30 129 CFU/tampon. It should be noted that when patients use Corega antiseptic soluble tablets as a method of hygienic care for removable dentures tabs, on the inner surface of orthopedic structures a larger species composition of microorganisms was found, such as α hemolytic Streptococcus, Enterococcus spp., Candida albicans, Candida other species, Lactobacellus spp. and Staphylococcus spp. to a degree exceeding lg 5.33±0.88 CFU/tampon. The results of the study are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of the composition of the microflora colonizing the inner surface of removable dentures when using the antiseptic drug Fargals and 1% Benzketozone and antiseptic soluble tablets Corega tabs after 1 week, (% , M±m)

Microorganisms	antiseptic drug Fargals and 1% Benzketozone (n=10)		Antiseptic dissolvable tablets Corega tabs (n=10)	
	Occurrence percentage	lg CFU/tampon	Occurrence percentage	lg CFU/tampon
α hemolytic Streptococcus	80.00%	4.88±0.30	50.00%	5.00±0.32
Enterococcus spp .	0.00%	0.00±0.00	30.00%	4.00±0.00
Candida albicans	0.00%	0.00±0.00	30.00%	4.00±0.00
Candida others species	0.00%	0.00±0.00	10.00%	4.00±0.00
Lactobacellus spp .	0.00%	0.00±0.00	30.00%	5.33±0.88
Staphylococcus spp	90.00%	4.44±0.18 p3-5=0.026	100.00%	5.30±0.33
Note: bold font - statistically significant differences at $p \leq 0.05$				

As a result of the studies, we can conclude that when 130 patients used the antiseptic drug Fargals and 1% Benzketozone for hygienic care of removable dentures , the composition of microorganisms colonizing the inner surface of removable orthopedic structures was statistically significantly different from the microflora determined on the inner surface of removable orthopedic structures. dentures when using antiseptic soluble tablets Corega tabs . Thus, the physical method of hygienic cleansing of removable dentures based on the antiseptic drug Fargals and 1% Benzketozone promotes better elimination of opportunistic flora colonizing removable orthopedic structures.

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